

MARKET POSITION OF INTERNATIONAL BIKES IN INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ROYAL ENFIELD

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Abstract:

This study will help to evaluate the present position of Royal Enfield among the existing customers and to identify the important reason why youngsters prefer Royal Enfield which is the most important feature of Royal Enfield. The respondents have also suggested modification required on existing models in the areas of product and services. The result show that majority of the respondents are satisfied with the purchase of bike in show rooms and are satisfied with the level of pickup of the bike. There is significant relationship between Age with the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike. But there is no significant relationship between Gender, Occupation with the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike. There is no significant relationship between Age, Gender and Occupation with the source of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike. Price modifications, mileage and flexibility to suit Indian roads are certain changes that are to be made to position the International Brand Royal Enfield in the Indian market.

Key Words: Customers, Satisfaction & Flexibility

Introduction:

In the initial years, entry of firms, capacity expansion, choice of products including capacity mix and technology, all critical areas of functioning of an industry, were effectively controlled by the State machinery.

However, the major set of reforms was launched in the year 1991 in response to the major macroeconomic crisis faced by the economy. The industrial policies shifted from a regime of regulation and tight control to a more liberalized and competitive era. Two major results of policy changes during these years in two-wheeler industry were that the, weaker players died out giving way to the new entrants and superior products and a sizeable increase in number of brands entered the market that compelled the firms to compete on the basis of product attributes

Classic Bikes with power for leisure riding is what a Royal Enfield bike stands for, and Royal Enfield leads this segment of the market in India by leaps and bounds. Its exquisite range of motorcycles combines distinctive styles with power, riding comfort and ruggedness to deliver a unique motorcycling experience. Mid 19th century England The firm of George Townsend & Co. opened its doors in the tiny village of Hunt End, near the Worcestershire town of Red ditch. The firm was specialized in sewing needles and machine parts. In the first flush of enterprise, flitting from one opportunity to another, they chanced upon the pedal-cycle trade.

Little did they know then that it was the beginning of the making of a leg end. Soon, George Townsend & Co. was manufacturing its own brand of bicycle. And in 1893 its products began to sport the name "Enfield" under the entity Enfield Manufacturing Company Limited with the trademark 'Made Like a Gun'. The marquee was born.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To evaluate the attitude of young generation towards Royal Enfield.
- ✓ To identify the factors influencing in selection of Royal Enfield.
- ✓ To analyze the problem of Royal Enfield while compared to other Bikes.
- ✓ To know the influence and impact of competitors.
- ✓ To study whether there is any change in perception of new generation towards Royal Enfield.
- ✓ To understand the reasons for change in perception, if any.
- ✓ To analyze the level of preference for new and old model of Royal Enfield.

Scope of the Study:

This study will helps to evaluate the present position of Royal Enfield among the existing customers. The study helps to identify the important reason why youngsters do likes Royal Enfield, which is the most important feature of Royal Enfield, in which way customers need modification on existing models, how is the level of customer acceptance in the areas of product and services. And also is there any kind of dissatisfaction in mind of existing customers and the reason for their dissatisfaction, etc...Simply the study makes a chance to the firm to delight their customers, ultimately for the existence and earnings in present corporate competition by

way of adjusting their products according to the customer needs, if necessary and also to know the strength, weakness, opportunity and threat of the product or the firm.

Period of the Study:

The study was conducted for a period of 6 months from September 2017 to February 2018.

Research Methodology:

A research design in the overall plan or program of research. A research design or model indicates a plan of action to be carried out in connection with a proposed research work.

Area of Study:

The area of the study is limited to Coimbatore city. It is popularly known as Manchester of south India, is situated in the western part of the state Tamil Nadu.

Statistical Tools Used:

Percentage Analysis & One Way ANOVA

Review of Literature:

Citation	Sample	Environment	Method	Conclusions
Ammer Arra Ahmed	100	Bangalore	Primary & Secondary Data	Conclusion The study has helped Royal Enfield bullet dealers to understand whether the customers are satisfied or not.
Devang Desai	50	Hyderabad	Primary & Secondary Data	Customers are very loyal towards the brand Royal Enfield bullet. Royal Enfield should concentrate on its advertising campaign to reach the customer the millage of Royal Enfield Bullet Bikes is very economical
Dinda	50	Moradabad	Primary & Secondary Data	This project is based on study the customer satisfaction towards toward bike of Royal Enfield in Moradabad .Customers are more demanding than the even before. Increase choices and access to more information on alternatives make it harder than ever before to win customers and retain existing clients in the face of stiff competition.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

	Particulars	No of Respondent	Percentage
Age	Below 18 Years	1	2.50%
	18 – 25 Years	36	90%
	25 – 35 Years	3	7.50%
	Total	40	100%
Gender	Male	30	75%
	Female	10	25%
	Total	40	100%
Occupation	Student	21	52.50%
	Professional	10	25%
	Private Employee	9	22.50%
	Total	40	100%
Annual Income	Less Than 1200000	30	75%
	120000 to 300000	8	20%
	300000 to 500000	2	5%
	Total	40	100%

Interpretation:

2.5% of respondents are under the age group of 18-25 years whereas 90% of the respondents are under the age group 25- 35 years 7.5% of the respondents are under the age group above 35 years.75% of the respondent are male as well as the remaining 25% of the respondents are female. 52.5% of respondents are under the occupation of student as well as 25% of the respondents are under the occupation of professional 22.5% of the respondents are under the occupation of private employee 0% of the respondents are under the occupation of government employee. 75% of respondents are under the annual income of less than 1200000 whereas 36.7% of the respondents are under the annual income of 1200000 to 300000 whereas 5% of the respondents are under the annual income of 300000 to 500000 0% of the respondents are under the annual income of above 500000.

ANOVA Table One Way Model:

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	Variance of F
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Between Sample	SSC	VI=C-1	MSC=SSC/(c-1)	
Within Sample	SSE	V2=n-c	MSE=SSE/(n-c)	MSC/MSE
Total	SST	n-1		

Association between Demographic Factors (Age, Gender & Occupation) and the Model of Royal Enfield Bike:

ANOVA Table						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age	Between Groups	.260	2	.130	1.915	.162
	Within Groups	2.515	37	.068		
	Total	2.775	39			
Gender	Between Groups	.390	2	.195	1.095	.345
	Within Groups	6.585	37	.178		
	Total	6.975	39			
Occupation	Between Groups	4.150	2	2.075	3.550	.039
	Within Groups	21.625	37	.584		
	Total	25.775	39			

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

H0: There is no significant relationship between Demographic Factors (Age, Gender & Occupation) and the Model of Royal Enfield Bike.

There is no significant relationship between Age, Gender with the selection of model of Royal Enfield Bike. But there is significant relationship between Occupation with the selection of model of Royal Enfield Bike.

Association between Demographic Factors (Age, Gender & Occupation) and the Mode of Purchase of Royal Enfield Bike:

ANOVA Table						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age	Between Groups	.275	1	.275	4.180	.048
	Within Groups	2.500	38	.066		
	Total	2.775	39			
Gender	Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.001	.971
	Within Groups	6.975	38	.184		
	Total	6.975	39			
Occupation	Between Groups	.043	1	.043	.063	.803
	Within Groups	25.732	38	.677		
	Total	25.775	39			

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

H0: There is no significant relationship between Demographic Factors (Age, Gender & Occupation) and the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike.

There is significant relationship between Age with the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike. But there is no significant relationship between Gender, Occupation with the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike.

Association between Demographic Factors (Age, Gender & Occupation) and the Source of Purchase of Royal Enfield Bike:

ANOVA Table						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age	Between Groups	.543	7	.078	1.112	.380
	Within Groups	2.232	32	.070		
	Total	2.775	39			
Gender	Between Groups	.814	7	.116	.604	.748
	Within Groups	6.161	32	.193		
	Total	6.975	39			
Occupation	Between Groups	5.446	7	.778	1.225	.318
	Within Groups	20.329	32	.635		
	Total	25.775	39			

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation:

H0: There is no significant relationship between Demographic Factors (Age, Gender & Occupation) and the Source of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike.

There is no significant relationship between Age, Gender and Occupation with the source of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike.

Findings and Suggestions:

Demographic Profile of the Respondents:

- ✓ The result show that the maximum 90% respondents are belong to the age of 18-25 years only
- ✓ The result shows that the maximum 75 % respondents are belong to male only
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 52.5% respondents are belong to the students only
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 75 % respondents are belong to the less than 120000 only
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 52.5% respondents are belong to classic 350 only
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 60% respondents are belong to the loan only
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 55% respondents do not consider other vehicles while purchasing Royal Enfield.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 60% respondents compare with Yamaha bike only.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 41% respondents get information from friends only.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 45% respondents have specified the mileage to be 40-45 only.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 62.5% respondents are satisfied with the mileage of bike.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 57.5% respondents say that breakdowns rarely happen.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 95% respondents purchase from the show room only
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 92.5% respondents are satisfied with the purchase of bike in showrooms.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 42.5% respondents have commented good for the level of pickup.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 52.5% respondents have commented good for comfort and safety of the bike.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 47.5% respondents have commented good for after sales service of the bike.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 32.5% respondent's friends comment about the bike as trendy model.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 80% respondents are satisfied with the complaint handling mechanism of the Company.
- ✓ The result show that the maximum 80% respondents suggest that the bike would suit Indian roads.

ANOVA:

- ✓ There is no significant relationship between Age, Gender with the selection of model of Royal Enfield Bike. But there is significant relationship between Occupation with the selection of model of Royal Enfield Bike.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between Age with the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike. But there is no significant relationship between Gender, Occupation with the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between Age, Gender and Occupation with the source of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The make and style of the vehicle is best suited for the young population of 18-25 years. Few modifications are to be made to suit other age categories also.
- ✓ The company should manufacture vehicles for women as majority of its vehicles suite only male population.
- ✓ Though the mileage is on the satisfactory level, when compared to other vehicles the mileage is quite low. Improvements are to be made for better mileage.
- ✓ Low priced vehicles are to be made available to suit all the consumers.
- ✓ Few technical changes are to be inculcated to suit Indian roads.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that there is significant relationship between Age with the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike. But there is no significant relationship between Gender, Occupation with the mode of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike. There is no significant relationship between Age, Gender and Occupation with the source of purchase of Royal Enfield Bike. Price modifications, mileage and flexibility to suit Indian roads are certain changes that are to be made to position the International Brand Royal Enfield in the Indian market.

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